

Research-in-Progress Paper

Co-producing applicable knowledge for mitigating transport-related air pollution: The Living lab approach of the MI-TRAP project

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Abstract

This paper presents a Living Lab approach to the co-production of knowledge on transport-related air pollution in urban environments, based on the results of the *Mitigating TRansport-related Air Pollution in Europe* (MI-TRAP) project, a HORIZON EUROPE Innovation Action. Recognising the limitations of top-down environmental policy and the need for inclusive, actionable recommendations, this Living Lab approach engages diverse stakeholders through a three-phase process: (1) co-creation of a shared vision and stakeholder identification, (2) participatory validation of proposed solutions, and (3) co-development of policy recommendations. Grounded in theories of co-production and real-world experimentation, the methodology integrates qualitative and quantitative data to facilitate collective learning and decision-making. Preliminary results from the first visioning phase demonstrate strong stakeholder engagement and early consensus on priority areas for intervention. This study contributes to the growing body of literature and fieldwork on Living Labs by offering a replicable model for addressing complex urban sustainability challenges through participatory innovation and transdisciplinary collaboration, specifically towards tackling transport-related urban air pollution.

Key words

Living Labs, Air Quality, Transport Emissions, European cities, Socio-technical Innovation, MI-TRAP Project

Introduction

Urban air pollution remains one of the most persistent and unequal public health challenges in Europe. Emissions from transport contribute significantly to harmful pollutants, such as nitrogen oxides (NO_x), particulate matter (PM₂₋₅ and PM₁₀), and black carbon, a fine soot primarily emitted from diesel engines. These pollutants are strongly linked to respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, disproportionately affecting children, older adults, and marginalised urban communities.

Acknowledging these risks, the newest EU Ambient Air Quality Directive (Directive 2024/2881) that entered into force on December 10th, 2024, aligns with the latest World Health Organisation guidelines, and forms part of broader efforts under the EU Zero Pollution Action Plan. However, despite increasing regulatory ambition, implementation at the local level often lags. Policy targets frequently outpace the institutional capacity, political will, and data accessibility required for effective action. A key part of the challenge lies in the limited understanding of the sources and pathways of transport-related air pollution at the urban scale. While advanced elemental and chemical analyses – such as black carbon tracing or source apportionment – can help identify the contribution of specific vehicle types, fuels, or braking systems, these insights are rarely integrated into local decision-making or effectively communicated to the most affected and vulnerable communities (European Environment Agency, 2025).

The MI-TRAP (Mitigating Transport-related Air Pollution in Europe) project, funded by HORIZON EUROPE, seeks to address this gap through a Living Lab approach that connects environmental science with urban governance and citizen engagement. Through the integration of scientific analysis with engagement processes, the proposed approach aims to produce knowledge that is both robust and socially grounded. Thereafter, the approach introduced, supports the identification of targeted and context-sensitive solutions while building trust, shared responsibility, and momentum. This paper presents the rationale, methodology, and preliminary results of this approach, offering a model for more inclusive and effective air quality governance in European cities.

Theoretical Approach

The theoretical approach of this research is grounded in the idea that complex, place-based challenges, such as transport-related air pollution require more than purely technical solutions. In this sense, they demand collaborative, systemic, and situated approaches to knowledge production. Central to this is the concept of knowledge co-

production (Kruijf et al., 2022), which challenges the traditional divide between expert knowledge and community perspectives. As such, it emphasises that robust, actionable knowledge emerges when diverse actors (including scientists, policymakers, and affected communities) work together throughout the research and decision-making process.

To operationalise this principle, MI-TRAP adopts a Living Lab framework, which represents a participatory, real-world setting that enables joint experimentation, mutual learning, and innovation. Living Labs are increasingly used in urban sustainability research, because they create opportunities to test solutions under real-life conditions, while engaging stakeholders in the framing and interpretation of the problem itself, shaping the problem and its framing (Beaudoin et al., 2022). Unlike traditional labs or policy pilots, Living Labs embrace uncertainty and iteration, making them particularly well-suited to multi-scalar, interdependent challenges like urban air quality that are shaped by mobility patterns, infrastructure systems, behavioural dynamics, and institutional arrangements.

This approach is further informed by the literature on real-world experimentation in cities, which position urban areas not only as sites of environmental crisis, but also as potential laboratories for societal transformation (Kampfmann et al., 2024). In this context, such approaches represent institutional and political experimentation arenas, where competing priorities and power relations are negotiated. In this light, air quality governance becomes a contested space, shaped by scientific evidence, policy, and public values.

Moreover, *MI-TRAP* aligns with emerging scholarship that frames urban transitions as fundamentally socio-technical. This includes attention to infrastructural lock-ins, regulatory inertia, and the need for inclusive, reflexive governance models (Hölscher & Frantzeskaki, 2021; Geels, 2012). As a result, in the field of transport-related air pollution, the approach of working at the interface of technical analysis (e.g. ultrafine particles monitoring, black carbon monitoring, elemental source attribution), development of innovation services (e.g. innovation toolkits) and participatory engagement supports the development of a Living Lab as a site not only for testing solutions, but also for reshaping relationships, practices, and responsibilities.

Methodology

This research adopts the Living Lab (LL) approach, a well-established methodology for open innovation and stakeholder-led experimentation, as practiced by the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL). The methodology is both rooted in the local context,

responding to the specific environmental, social, and governance realities at the local level, and international scope, enabling shared learning across a diverse range of urban environments. MI-TRAP activities are implemented in ten City Pilots, and specifically: Athens/Piraeus, Zurich, Milan, Florence, Berlin, Copenhagen/Aarhus, Lisbon, Prague, Lille/Dunkirk, and Rotterdam. Each one of these cities faces context-specific challenges in relation to transport, pollution, and mobility, making them ideal settings for both local experimentation and comparative analysis.

As part of the Living Lab approach, knowledge is generated through direct engagement with local actors via interviews, focus groups, and facilitated workshops. These efforts are supported by an international platform that brings together participants from all City Pilots in recurring horizontal workshops. These sessions are designed to share experiences, promote reflection on common challenges and build a shared understanding of effective practices in the field. They also help link local-level engagement reality with broader European environmental goals.

Throughout the process, attention is also given to involving diverse voices, using accessible formats to present technical findings, such as air quality measurements, innovative instrumentation, health impacts and mitigation factors. The MI-TRAP Living Lab approach supports an ongoing exchange among citizens, scientists, industries and decision-makers. This collaborative process helps both to test and refine solutions, as well as to identify barriers and opportunities within each local system. Overall, it provides the framework for developing policy recommendations that are grounded in evidence and co-created knowledge, and that reflect the real needs and capacities of each city involved.

In this direction, the MI-TRAP International Living Lab represents an innovative approach by emphasizing capacity building through the clear communication of newly generated air quality data. Through the deployment of advanced instruments to measure ultrafine particles and black carbon, the project produces novel insights into pollutants that are often misunderstood, complicating policy responses. Crucially, MI-TRAP International Living Lab translates these complex data into accessible information for policymakers, municipal authorities, and citizens, enabling meaningful engagement and informed decision-making. This integration of cutting-edge scientific monitoring with participatory knowledge co-production strengthens the implementation of the revised EU Ambient Air Quality Directive (Directive 2024/2881) and its translation into national and local contexts, thereby extending both the reach and impact of the Living Lab model.

Results from the 1st International Living Lab Workshop

Before exploring shared challenges, the MI-TRAP project activities began by identifying the starting context (or “maturity level”) of each participating city in relation to transport-related pollution, air quality governance, citizen engagement, and policy innovation. These assessments were based on interviews/ group discussions conducted with representatives and external stakeholders from the project’s City Pilots. The local realities shaped the design of the first International Living Lab workshop that followed, which brought together stakeholders across Europe to identify knowledge gaps, explore future air quality scenarios, and map key actors for innovation. Here, co-creation exercises were implemented based on three thematic areas: knowledge barriers and policy implications; scenario-building for air quality futures; and key stakeholders for innovation building.

City Contexts and Challenges based on interviews with MI-TRAP city pilots representatives

Each city presented distinct environmental, social, and political conditions. Athens, surrounded by mountains and affected by both vehicle emissions and dust storms, faces compounded air quality challenges. Rotterdam, shaped by its shipping industry and port operations, is making progress on emissions control, but still lacks comprehensive data. In Milan, urban morphology conditions and emissions from traffic and agriculture concentrate pollutants in the Po Valley. Lisbon faces vehicle and airport emissions, but benefits from strong civil society involvement. Zurich, while performing well on sustainability metrics, now faces rising non-exhaust emissions. In Berlin, a flat landscape and dense traffic make air quality a persistent issue despite policy efforts. In Florence and Prague, traffic and domestic heating are major contributors, with growing citizen interest in local initiatives. Copenhagen and Aarhus benefit from declining pollution levels thanks to cycling infrastructure and public transport, while community engagement remains a strength.

Results from the 1st International Living Lab Workshop

As indicated in Figure 1 below, a key finding was the widespread presence of knowledge gaps - particularly in public awareness, scientific understanding of pollutants like ultrafine particles and non-exhaust emissions, and the effective translation of evidence into policy. These gaps vary by city; for example, Zurich prioritised data on rail-related pollution, while Athens sought better tools for visualising neighbourhood-level exposure.

Scenario-building exercises highlighted cautious optimism about improving air quality, driven by regulation and innovation. However, participants also expressed concern about emerging pollutants, unequal policy enforcement, and rising health disparities. Education, citizen science, and political will were seen as essential to future progress.

Stakeholder mapping revealed the need to engage underrepresented groups, particularly in industry and health. Cities identified new opportunities for collaboration and proposed more targeted outreach, setting the direction for the next MI-TRAP Living Lab workshop focused on validating practical tools and co-designed solutions.

Figure 1. Schematic Representation of the 1st International Living Lab Workshop results

Discussion and Conclusion

The first MI-TRAP International Living Lab workshop revealed that addressing air pollution requires not only better data or stricter regulation, but a deeper transformation in how urban systems integrate knowledge, governance, and public engagement. These findings confirm that improving air quality is a socio-technical challenge. Solutions are not purely technological, but they require new ways of organising collaboration between actors, integrating data into urban planning, and aligning between short-term decisions and long-term public health and environmental goals.

MI-TRAP contributes to this shift by developing tools that reflect both scientific rigour and user needs: real-time pollution maps, emission impact assessment models, health risk assessment, planning platforms for nature-based solutions and citizen-science methodologies. These tools directly respond to the needs and priorities identified during the workshop, particularly the demand for actionable, transparent, and locally adaptable information. As a result, the MI-TRAP International Living Lab approach strengthens evidence-based policymaking by translating advanced monitoring and health data into accessible formats for local use.

This combination is distinctive: adding to existing literature and practical applications (Alimbene et al., 2022) that suggest that Living Labs can promote innovative approaches to design an urban-scale air-quality management plan, MI-TRAP embeds cutting-edge measurement technologies directly into policy processes, making the Living Lab an integral part of technological innovation. The approach can influence local strategies (e.g. to inform revisions of their Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (SUMP), particularly on priority exposure areas and mitigation pathways like low-emission zones and modal shift measures). The multi-city design is another source of novelty, enabling comparison and learning across ten diverse urban contexts while building a shared European platform for policy innovation. This networked structure allows findings from one city to be tested and adapted in others, accelerating knowledge transfer and supporting implementation of the revised EU Ambient Air Quality Directive at national and municipal levels. Though still at an early (visioning) stage, the project offers a replicable model for embedding citizen-driven and scientifically rigorous innovation into urban governance, laying the groundwork for deeper digital integration and long-term transformative change.

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

The upcoming ILL workshop will focus on validating these solutions as well as shape how these tools are refined, implemented, and embedded into local governance processes advancing socio-technical innovation through collaborative tool development and institutional learning across Europe's urban environments.

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